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PERSISTENT FARMERS/HERDERS CONFLICT IN NIGERIA: A FOUNDATIONAL ORIGIN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

The persistent conflict between farmers and herders in Nigeria represents a significant challenge to national security and development. This study investigates the root causes and dynamics of these conflicts through the lens of the frustration-aggression theory, which posits that aggression is a result of individuals' frustration from unfulfilled needs. Using secondary data and extensive literature review, this paper examines farmers and herders conflict in Nigeria. The analysis reveals that the lack of restorative justice measures has rendered traditional conflict resolution mechanisms ineffective. Findings indicate that government actions have often been punitive rather than conciliatory, thereby increasing frustration among affected communities and fueling further aggression. The study concludes that implementing restorative justice, which focuses on reconciliation and the restoration of relationships, could provide a more sustainable resolution to the farmers-herders conflict. Recommendations include integrating restorative justice principles into national conflict resolution strategies to mitigate violence, foster mutual understanding, and promote enduring peace and development in Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Despite the frequent conflicts which now characterise farmers-herdsmen relations in Nigeria, farmers and herdsman relations have co-existed over the centuries across West Africa (Davidheiser & Luna 2024). These relations had been peaceful in the main, and largely harmonious and complementary. The relations have reflected several processes involved in pastoralism and cultivation which are the economic mainstays of the groups. Pastoralists have over the centuries depended on foliage from farmers for their cattle and staple food while farmers depend on dung manure for their farms, and meat and dairy products from cattle. This symbiotic relationship has marked the centuries of harmony and understanding between the two groups. Blench (2010, cited in Olayoku 2021) gave instances of 'economic

exchange of dairy products for grains, access to local markets and the provision of manure on arable land while the cattle consumed crop residues'. Pastoralists and farmers are interrelated because they share land, water, fodder and other resources (Shettima & Tar 2018).

This complementary relationship has now given way to conflict that has on many occasions driven the corporate existence of the Nigerian state to the brink of disintegration. The recent armed clashes in Plateau, and in Benue, Anambra, Enugu, Ondo, Ekiti and virtually every other state in Nigeria, show how, almost irretrievably, farmers-herdsmen relations have broken down. With climate change and reduced land due to population increase, there has arisen a situation of acute shortage and unavailability of pasture and water, which are needed by pastoralists and also by farmers in Nigeria. The ethnic and religious configurations of the two groups have also served to fuel the embers of discord among them. The fact that the vast majority of the herdsmen are Hausa-Fulani and Muslims, and the farmers are mainly Christians and non-Hausa-Fulani, has served to complicate the crisis. There is also a regional dimension to the conflict. The herdsmen are from the North while the farmers can be located southwards.

Statement of the Problem

Herdsmen generally move their cattle to where they can get fodder. This movement of cattle is affected by seasonal changes in climate. During the dry season, there is a movement of herdsmen and their cattle down south. Then at the return of the rains, they move back northwards. These migratory movements of herdsmen have been occasioned by violent clashes between them and farmers along the routes. The farmers claim damage to their crops in different parts of the country. Both farmers and herdsmen claim rights in this matter. First, both groups have citizenship rights. Herdsmen have expressed strong feelings against the attempts to obstruct the free movement of their men and cattle in different parts of the country. This means the violation of the 'cow rights' of the herdsmen who are of the view that they should have unfettered movement across the country (Okoli, & Atelhe, 2024). On the other hand, farmers feel they deserve the right to engage in their farming occupation without disturbance from outside. Farmers across the country have accused herdsmen of destroying their farms and exposing them to huge economic losses.

This atmosphere of misgivings has fuelled repeated attacks between farmers and herdsmen. Throughout the country, these hitherto harmonious and complementary groups are now at loggerheads. The conflict, which has become almost intractable, has claimed hundreds of lives as well as displaced thousands of other Nigerians. This has further exposed the conflict resolution mechanisms of the Nigerian state as inadequate. Both farmers and herdsmen have expressed deep feelings of injustice concerning the matter. Both groups feel abandoned by government and the society at large and have increasingly resorted to self-help. This in effect has made resolution efforts by stakeholders very difficult. While the need for justice is felt both by the farmers and the herdsmen, conventional mechanisms for delivering justice have not really served to bring peace and harmony to the affected communities. It is this continuing crisis between farmers and herdsmen in Nigeria, and the difficulties in resolving the crisis, that this study seeks to explore. With the obvious inadequacies of the conventional criminal justice system and a host of other mechanisms that should have arrested the descent into anarchy.

Objectives of the Study

This study investigates the root causes of the persistent farmers/herders conflict in Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

- i. To identify the foundational origins of the persistent farmers/herders conflict in Nigeria.
- ii. Explore methods that could provide a more sustainable resolution to the farmers-herders conflict

LITERATURE REVIEW

Farmers-Herders Conflict in Nigeria

The persistent conflict between herders and farmers has a long and complex historical background. The disputes on land related matters among the herders and the rural farmers are nothing new. However, the conflict has transformed by time and turned into a destructive and violent conflict since the beginning of 21st century (Ekperchukwu, & Carla, 2021) The increase in farmers-herders conflicts in the last decade has been a source of concern. The conflict between these major actors in the agricultural sector is one of the Nigeria's most persistent security challenges threatening the peace and stability of the country as it has left many people dead in recent times. Destruction of lives and properties has almost become a daily activities in most agrarian communities from the Northern to Southern parts of the country. These developments have discouraged both local and foreign investors from investing in the country agricultural sector and also impacting the government economic diversification initiatives negatively thereby threatening the fabrics of the country's economy.

Clarification of Concept

Herdsman-Farmers Conflict Herdsman-Farmer Conflict refers to the violent confrontations and clashes that occur between two distinct groups in Nigeria: farmers and herders (Francis, Kenneth, & Nkama, 2022). Farmers are individuals whose primary occupation revolves around cultivating land and growing crops for both personal consumption and commercial purposes (Erunke & Aku, 2022). They may also rear livestock such as poultry and cattle. While some farmers may have their own farms using modern machinery or hired farm laborers, others may travel with their labor as a commodity, seeking markets to earn income and support their families. On the other hand, herders, also known as Fulani pastoralists, are nomadic individuals whose main livelihood involves raising livestock, particularly cows and sheep, for commercial gain (Erunke & Aku, 2022). They move from one area to another, seeking green pastures and water sources for their animals without a fixed pattern of movement (Francis, Kenneth, & Nkama, 2022).

Theoretical Perspective

This paper is anchored in the Frustration-Aggression model of conflict theory. The frustration-aggression theory, initially proposed by Dollard, Miller, Doob, Mowrer, and Sears in 1939 and later refined by Berkowitz in 1969, suggests that aggression arises as a result of blocking or frustrating a person's efforts to achieve a goal (Breuer & Elson, 2017). Originally, the theory stated that frustration always leads to aggression, but it was later re-formulated to suggest that while frustration creates a need to respond, aggression is just one possible outcome. However, aggression is deemed a necessary condition for frustration (Breuer & Elson, 2017). Frustration-aggression theory posits that aggression is an outcome of frustration, which arises when an individual's goal-directed behavior is thwarted. The core

assumption is that frustration produces an aggressive drive that motivates behavior intended to injure the source of the frustration (Francis, Bawa, & Haruna, 2019). This theory suggests that when individuals are unable to achieve their desired outcomes due to obstacles or interferences, the resulting frustration can lead to aggressive actions as a means of expressing or alleviating that frustration.

One strength of the frustration-aggression theory is its ability to explain the underlying psychological mechanism driving aggressive behaviors. It provides a clear causal link between frustration and aggression, offering insights into why people may react violently in certain situations. The theory has been influential in various fields, including psychology, sociology, and conflict studies, helping to shape interventions and policies aimed at reducing violence by addressing sources of frustration. However, the theory also has notable weaknesses. It tends to oversimplify the complex nature of human aggression by suggesting a direct, inevitable link between frustration and aggression. In reality, not all frustration leads to aggression, and other factors such as individual differences, social context, and cultural norms play significant roles. Additionally, the theory does not adequately account for non-aggressive responses to frustration, such as problem-solving or emotional coping strategies. Applying the frustration-aggression theory to the herdsman and farmers conflicts in Nigeria provides a useful framework for understanding the dynamics at play. The competition over land and resources, coupled with environmental changes and economic pressures, creates significant frustration for both herdsman and farmers. Herdsman, facing diminishing grazing lands and water sources, often encroach on farmlands, leading to destruction of crops and loss of livelihood for farmers. This encroachment generates frustration among farmers, who may respond aggressively to protect their land and resources. Conversely, herdsman may also resort to aggression when they feel their way of life is threatened. The theory highlights how these frustrations can escalate into violent confrontations, emphasizing the need for policies that address the root causes of frustration, such as resource scarcity and equitable land use management, to mitigate the conflict.

METHODOLOGY

The data collection method involved the collection and review of books, online materials, Newspapers and a wide range of materials. In addition, an online search for “farmers and herdsman clashes in Nigeria” was carried out in order to assess any pattern of search showing interest on the implication of the issue.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Different factors range from the environmental to political, religious, and ethnicity have been identified as driven forces driving farmers-herders conflicts, but at their center is the problem of land scarcity. The challenge of climate change and desertification has forced herdsman down South from the North to feed and sell their cattle. In the process of searching for food for their cattle, the herders encroached on farm lands, destroying crops thereby leading to violent conflict. Corroborating this assertion, the umbrella body of the cattle breeders in Nigeria, the Mayetti Allah Cattle Breeders Association (MACBAN), agreed that the effect of climate change and desertification was a major causal factor leading to trans-human movement from Northern part to the South annually which has resulted in a lot of conflict between the farmers and herders (Okoli, & Addo, 2018). Also, Olusola (2024) attributed farmers-herders conflicts to infrastructural development, cattle theft and change in pastoralist system. He assert that farmers are losing vast arable of lands to government

infrastructural development causing them to look for new land for farming and growing business sector building on grazing routes for animal. Furthermore, while the farmers accused the herdsman of destroying their crops by failing to control their animals, at the same time the, herdsman alleged that the farming communities were rustling their cattle. Another driving reason for the conflict between herders and farmers is the changes in pastoralist system as some pastoralist herders have changed to sedentary lifestyle. This led to the using of underage and younger herdsman who are not experience in grazing and negotiation techniques with the farmers like the elderly herders for grazing and walking of animal. To [Ogunddele, Musa & Sule \(2020\)](#) impunity and Poor governance are the major factors aggravating the conflict, because the armed groups who attack farmers and villages most of the time do not face any penalties and charges. They are not even arrested by the police leading to farmers and other victims resulting to self-help. Since the emergence of President Muhammadu Buhari, the conflict between the farmers and herders took both religious and ethnic dimensions. There were allegations must especially by the Southerners who are mostly Christians that the conflict is more than a mere struggle for scarce resources but an attempt to extend the Fulani dominance to other parts of the country and to Islamise the country. There were allegation that the president body language is encouraging the killer herders and has always been supporting them. For instance, in 2000, there was a report that the president visited the then governor of Oyo State, Alhaji Lam Adesina and asked for compensation for the Fulani herders over a conflict between them and the farmers. Also in 2021, the president announced that his government would reclaim all the grazing routes across the country to allow the Fulani herdsman move their cattle freely. The statement by the president does not go down well with the Southerners which they claimed it was a deliberate attempt to encourage his Fulani people to disobey the ban on open grazing by the Southern governors.

Prior to the violent conflict between the farmers and herders leading to loss of lives and properties, for decades, there has been a cordial, peaceful and harmonious relationship among famers and herders across communities in Nigeria, except for few cases of disagreements which never led to the destruction of lives and properties nor affect economic activities which would later be solved by negotiations and usually the heads of villages and herder communities agreed on simple solutions such as a herder must compensate the damage in a farm if he couldn't control his animals and prevent them damaging the growing crops ([Nnaji & Samuel, 2019](#)). However, the collapse of the old traditional approach to settlement through negotiation between the two groups has led to violent conflict as the one with more sophisticated weapon try to get what they want without negotiating with other and this has led to the loss of many lives and others have been displaced from their homes.

Report from the Nigerian Security database shown that, from 6274 conflicts recorded from January 2014 – December 2020, 309 were farmers-herders conflicts related leading to the death of 3087 people across the country which represent about 5 per cent of violent conflicts in Nigeria ([Adigun, 2022](#)). Also, data from the Nextier Security, Peace and Development Violent Conflict Database shows that from October 2020-September 2021, conflict between farmers-herders occurred 71 times, accounting for 406 deaths across the country. The North-Central remains the worst hit region of the farmers-herders conflicts followed by the North-West, Southwest, South- East and South-South respectively in terms of incidents and casualties ([Akinwumi, 2023](#)).

Over the years, successive government have put in place measures to mitigate the farmers –herders conflict, but have not yielded any positive results, as most of the measures were either alleged to be in favour of the herders or farmers, this allegation from both sides makes efforts at resolving it by both state and non-state actors difficult. For instance, the Goodluck Jonathan led administration in 2014 inaugurated an inter-ministerial technical committee on grazing reserve. The committee recommended the recovery and improvement of all grazing routes encroached by farmers across the country. It further recommended the immediate release of a sum of N100 billion by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) for ranch construction. However, the failure of the Goodluck Jonathan government to win the 2015 general election led to the non-implementation of the committee reports. Also in 2016, the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) advised the president Buhari government to set a short, medium and long term strategic plan which will encourage the development of grazing route across the country. This proposal was vehemently rejected by most states in the middle belt and southern parts of the country, they alleged that the plan was an attempt to handover their land to the Fulani herdsman. The FMARD in March 2016 also announced the proposal to import grass from Brazil on the grazing reserve in order to increase the consumption of grass by cattle and boost their output. This pronouncement did not go down well with many Nigerian as it was seeing as a waste of public funds. In February 2018, highest policy making body in Nigeria, the National Executive Council (NEC), constituted a sub-committee to examine herder-farmer conflicts. Based on the recommendation of the committee, the NEC approved that open grazing of cattle in Nigeria should be banned. Also as part of the effort to arrest the herders-farmers conflict in their respective states, the 17 state governors in southern Nigeria and the governor of Benue and Taraba States in the North Central zone banned open grazing, but the federal government viewed the ban differently, and thus it does not exist in practice (Nomor, & Ominyi, 2022).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The foregoing shows that notwithstanding the present intensity of farmers herdsman conflict in Nigeria, the phenomenon can be resolved if the right things are done by those responsible for doing them. The federal government must now take the lead and ensure that grazing laws are enacted for the entire country. The state governments can also make complementary laws, and local governments, complementary by-laws. These laws will clearly provide for ranches and define grazing lands and must mark out grazing routes across the country. The federal government should also develop the legal structure and framework for restorative justice, to complement the extant criminal justice system in the country and encourage farmers and herdsman to bring their misgivings to the constituted authority. Errant farmers and herdsman must be made to pay reparation and victims must be properly compensated.

There is also an urgent need to define citizenship more clearly in the country, such that Nigerians are identifiable and know their rights. Foreigners must also have their rights clearly stipulated and need to be easily distinguished even in cases they are from adjacent countries but have kin in Nigeria. The herder- farmer divide must not be exacerbated by lack of clear guidelines for citizens and non-citizens.

Efforts at population control should be intensified in the country. National population policy had earlier pegged the number of maximum births per woman at 4, but implementation and enforcement have been lacking. In the light of the population explosion

problems confronting the country, the policy must not only be enforced immediately, but it should also be redefined so that the limit is per man as this is what will truly curtail population growth.

Restorative justice committees must be created and promoted, offering parties a place to air their grievances and seek redress where necessary. Such committees should include environmental professionals who can orientate the farmers and herdsman on best practices even within the situation of climate change.

Finally, there is an urgent need to define citizenship more clearly in the country, such that Nigerians are identifiable and they know their rights, while foreigners can easily be identified and restrained according to the laws of the country, even if they have ethnic kin across the borders in Nigeria.

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